

Determining Factors Influencing Consumers' Purchase Decisions for Green Products: An Analytical Study of Delhi

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Abstract:

Literature related to green consumer behavior mostly has focused on South Asian markets. Although environmental awareness among Indian consumers has been observed in the literature, but their purchase behavior towards green products is not yet clearly recognized. Thus, the purpose of this research study is to examine the variables influencing Indian customers' decisions to buy green products. The current study uses a survey-based methodology to test a set of hypotheses. Using a 27-items questionnaire and snowball sampling methodology, data were collected from 204 Indian

respondents in Delhi. Data were analyzed using exploratory factor analysis and regression method was used to test the proposed hypotheses. The findings showed that respondents are willing to search for environmental protection, realization of environmental responsibilities and green product-related information and learn about green products. Not only this, striving for environmental protection, motivation for environmental responsibility, green product past-experience, environmental friendly nature of companies and social influence or peer group influence are identified as important factors influencing green product purchase decisions. Thus, this study provides valuable insights into green consumer behavior in the Indian context by examining the factors that influence consumers' purchase decisions towards green products.

Keywords: *Green Products, Environmental awareness, Environmental protection, Consumer behavior, Consumer purchase decisions.*

Introduction

Cognizance about the havoc of natural resources as a result of human activities has raised the issue of environmental protection and environmental consciousness in consumer behavior, which increase the demand for green products in the market across the world. A product that consumers prefer because it helps protect the environment during the manufacture, use and disposal of the product—is called a green product. Green products are often defined as organic, environmentally friendly, recyclable,

and energy-efficient products. Greening occurs throughout a product's life cycle, from design and raw material acquisition to production, storage, transit, usage, and post-usage activities. Most scholars such as Matsumoto et al. (2017) have discussed the consumption aspects of green products throughout their life cycle. Since consumer market knowledge and the variables motivating green purchase behavior have been found to have significant implications (Melander, 2020), scholars have been trying to understand the nature of green consumers in different markets. Literature related to consumer

behavior theories and models, addresses environmental aspects of consumption patterns, discusses in detail the demand for environmentally friendly products and motivates business organizations to adopt environmentally friendly behaviors in order to survive in the market (Czainska, et al. 2021). Studies on green consumer behavior, using and testing samples from multiple cities, countries, and inter-countries, have observed growing consumers' environmental awareness. Studies have examined how consumers make informed choices about green products and have attempted to develop an understanding of the determinants of their behavior and purchasing habits. These empirical studies have focused on the determinants of environmentally friendly purchase behavior such as purchase intentions, purchase decisions, actual purchase behavior, and willingness to pay. As green consumerism is gradually moving towards Global South regions (Lee, 2008, Yum-Tang and Chan, 1998), India has been one of them as a potential market for green products (Singh, 2004, 2013).

To date, research conducted in the Indian context has concentrated on two areas: the factors that influence consumers' purchasing behavior and food choices, specifically products like genetically modified and organic food (Mediratta & Mathur, 2023; Singh & Verma, 2017) and their attitudes toward green practices

in the lodging industry (Sudhagar, 2015). Findings of studies show that Indian consumers prefer products and services of environmentally friendly companies (Nath et al., 2012 ; Mandal & Paul, 2012), and are becoming selective in their buying behavior in terms of preference for green products, their competitive prices, product quality, and their responsiveness in retail stores (Singh et al., 2012 ; Chaudhary, 2018). As environmental awareness has been improving in the Indian market (Jaiswal et al., 2022), so, there is a need to understand the factors influencing environmentally friendly purchase decision-making when purchasing green products.

Review of Literature

A green consumer is an individual who chooses goods and services that have a neutral or minimal impact on the environment. In the current state of research on green consumer behavior, the purchasing decision of green consumers has been found to be a central topic. Purchase decisions of the green consumers have been described as being more likely to support green companies, purchase green products (Narula & Desore, 2016), adopt sustainable consumption practices (Nekmahmud & Fekete-Farkas, 2020) and spend more for green products (Wei et al., 2018).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework for Green Product Purchase Decision

Green consumers' purchase decisions are broadly influenced by two factors. One set of factors is inherent to consumers such as their realization of environmental responsibilities, desire to acquire knowledge, self-interest and the willingness to act to conserve resources and have a reduced impact on the environment. And others are external to the consumer that relate to consumers' social image and product attributes (such as product quality, safety, performance, price, promotion, and effects on human health) (Pilgrimienè et al., 2020). Actual behavior is the result of situational factors such as consumers' routine habits, their product knowledge, culture, demographic characteristics; and promotional campaigns (Young et al., 2010). The variables from the literature are identified in this study (Figure 1), and they are described as follows.

Factors Influencing Consumers' Purchase Decisions for Green Products

Endorsing Environmental Protection (EEP)

Endorsing environmental protection is one of the major factors for consumers to behave environmentally friendly in their purchase decisions (Mishra & Kulshreshtha, 2023). Consumers look for environmentally beneficial features related to product design and product use that have a low impact on the environment and make a meaningful difference in environmental protection (Paparoidamis, et al., 2019). Apart from this, Consumers look for products that are not harmful to animals and nature, have recyclable components, and cause less environmental pollution during their usage. It means consumers demand eco-friendly products. Thus, they recognize the role of green products in improving environmental quality and they show advocacy for environmental protection by purchasing and owning green products. They are also able to associate the appropriateness of the higher prices of green products with the environmental benefits they provide. In this way, green products add relevance to their environmentally friendly

lifestyle (Kumar & Ghodeswar, 2015) and develop a positive attitude in consumers' minds. Thus, Consumers show a preference for environmentally friendly products compared to non-green products and demonstrate their positive attitude by actually purchasing such products (Yadav & Pathak, 2016).

Perceived Environmental Responsibility (PER)

Striving for environmental responsibility refers to consumers' self-commitment to environmental protection issues and their individual-level activities aimed at improving environmental quality. Consumers are aware of their own self-responsibilities for environmental protection as they recognize the negative impact of the environment on humans and other living beings (Pawaskar et al., 2018). They feel emotionally connected to environmental protection issues (Sherman et al., 1997) and believe that they can personally contribute to environmental protection by adopting environmentally friendly activities at the individual level. They are motivated by an underlying concern about the well-being of the planet and its inhabitants and are found to be primarily engaged in environmental protection (Taufique, 2022). Their environmental concern, compassion, and belief in the existence of environmental problems at the individual level motivate them to behave in an environmentally friendly manner (Chen, et al., 2020; Perera et al., 2022) and shift their purchasing patterns toward green products.

Consumers' Past Experience with Green Products (CPEGP)

Consumers' past purchase and usage experience with green products is another influential variable affecting green product purchase decisions. It is related to consumers' curiosity to gain knowledge about the environmental aspects of green products. For this, consumers try to learn about green products themselves and acquire knowledge related to the ingredients of green products, the impact of products on the environment and the functionality of the product, etc. (Sheikh, et al., 2014). In addition,

they share knowledge and information about green products with their friend-circles and learn from each other (Tavitiyaman et al., 2024). Customers can comprehend the positive environmental impacts of eco-friendly products through product evaluation, which is a by-product of the learning process and leads to the development of eco-friendly product sensitivity. This increases their willingness to pay more for environmentally friendly products, influences their purchasing decisions even more, and helps them make the best judgments possible (Biswas & Roy, 2016).

Environmental Friendly Nature of Companies (EFNC)

Environmentally concerned consumers have been asking corporations/companies to pay attention to environmental issues and design their products and processes with a lower impact on the environment for a long time (Wong et al., 1996; Pedro & Lemke, 2013). As a result, businesses design products that are less hazardous to the environment, use environmentally friendly production processes and operations, and follow national and international legislation (Wong et al., 2012). Many manufacturing organizations or companies make products ecologically friendly by substituting hazardous materials with environmentally friendly or environmentally safe ingredients or by reducing the amount of harmful ingredients without harming the product's overall function. Gradually, recognition, praise, and promotion of environmentally friendly companies are reflected in the purchase decisions of environmentally conscious consumers. Now, at the time of purchasing, green consumers read the ingredient labels of products to check the impact of the product on the environment. Not only this, consumers also look at whether a green product consumes fewer inputs in terms of energy and resources during its use. Just because of this, they are more likely to refuse to buy products from polluting companies and boycott companies that do not comply with environmental regulations or that exploit the green movement to increase sales (Liao & Liu, 2022).

Social Influence (SI)

Social influence is characterized as "a shift in an individual's attitudes, behaviors, thoughts, or feelings as a result of interacting with other individuals or groups." Consumer behavior is highly influenced by the opinions of others regarding their product choices and usage (Kim & Srivastava, 2007). Consumers develop and perceive the importance of products when they interact with others and gather relevant information (Wang et al., 2011). Consumers, as part of a community or social group, obtain and share information, learn what other people think about a particular product and evaluate products based on the comments and points of view of others (Indra et al., 2020). Thus, consumers understand and describe their needs, tastes, and preferences. (Puetz, 2015). In addition, consumers are generally attracted to products that develop their self-perception and the way they want to be viewed by others (Sun et al., 2022). Therefore, social influence is also found to be influential in developing their product preferences (Wang, 2014). Hence, they intend to purchase products that adhere to society's perceptions (Mishra & Kulshreshtha, 2023) as well as build their social-identity (Silintowe et al., 2023), because, consumers widely believe that behaving in an environmentally friendly manner is a modern way of living and prestige and, if they do not behave in this way, they will be considered outdated in society (Vysotska & Vysotskyi, 2022; Griskevicius, et al., 2010). Therefore, purchase decisions of green products communicate consumers' environmental-friendliness (self-image) and demonstrate their concerns for environmental protection to comply with social pressure (social image) (Sadiq et al., 2021). Thus, consumers perceive the benefit of preferring "green", which increases their desirability of high-value green products (van Dam & Fischer, 2015) and strongly influences their purchase decisions.

Hypotheses of the Study

Therefore, the following hypotheses can be proposed:

H1. Endorsing Environmental Protection (EEP) significantly has an impact on consumers' green product purchase decisions (GPPD).

H2. *Perceived* Environmental Responsibility (PER) significantly has an impact on consumers' green product purchase decisions (GPPD).

H3. Consumers' Past Experience with Green Products (CPEGP) significantly has an impact on consumers' green product purchase decisions (GPPD).

H4. Environmental Friendly Nature of Companies (EFNC) significantly has an impact on consumers' green product purchase decisions (GPPD).

H5. Social Influence (SI) significantly has an impact on consumers' green product purchase decisions (GPPD).

Methodology

The questionnaire method was preferred because it allows for collecting many responses quickly. A questionnaire (Google form) was circulated to respondents. Thus, to test and quantify the hypothesized relationships, a questionnaire-based survey approach was adopted. The questionnaire consisting of 27 items was composed of two sections. All measurements in the study were subjective assessments by respondents using a five-point Likert-type scale (end points 1 strongly disagree and 5 strongly agree). The second part collected data was related to the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Demographic measures such as age, gender, academic qualification, and occupation, were included. The sample in this study was initially selected using a snowball

sampling technique that relies on chain referrals to find eligible participants. People were contacted by phone or in person and asked if they were willing to participate in the study. This study was conducted in Delhi, India. Respondents were randomly selected regardless of education level, occupation, income and other demographic characteristics. Consumers were approached in different parts of the city or

district of Delhi. A total of 204 valid responses were received from the 330 consumers contacted. Of these, 103 (50.4 per cent) were males and 101 (49.5 per cent) were females. The demographic characteristics are mentioned in Table 1. The data were analyzed using exploratory factor analysis to identify and validate the items contributing to each factor. In addition, hypothesis testing using Regression model fit was performed to test the relationships of the identified variables with consumers' green product purchase decisions. These tests were interpreted based on the support obtained from the literature.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the respondents

Demographic Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	103	50.4
Female	101	49.5
<i>Age (in years)</i>		
20-30	39	19.1
31-40	46	22.5
41-50	43	21.0
51-60	45	22.0
Above 60	31	15.1
<i>Academic Qualification</i>		
Higher Secondary	6	02.9
Graduate	92	45.0
Post-Graduate and above	106	51.9
<i>Occupational Status</i>		
Student	30	14.7
Self-employed	72	35.2
Private Job	76	37.2
Govt. Job	26	12.7
Total	204	100

Analysis and Findings

The analyses were started by converting data into numeric form and tabulating the data collected in an MS Excel sheet, followed by SPSS software. The reliability of the questionnaire was calculated, followed by factor analyses and hypothesis testing. The findings are then laid out in the next step.

Reliability Analysis

Reliability analysis (Table 2) revealed Cronbach's α value for the questionnaire as 0.779 and is comparable with the reliabilities reported by (Wadkar et al., 2016).

Table 2. Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.779	27

Adequacy of Sampling

Principal component analysis and varimax rotation were utilized to analyze the scale factorization. The result of Bartlett's test of sphericity was 0.000 and the KMO value was 0.772 (See Table 3), which meets the assumption of factorability.

Table 3. KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.772
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1356.627
	df	300
	Sig.	.000

Factor Analysis

In the exploratory factor analysis, items with factor loadings greater than 0.5 were retained. The variables were grouped into six factors (Table 4) and together accounted for 67.056 percent of the total variance.

Table 4. Exploratory Factor analysis

Items	Alpha-Value	Factor Loading
Factor 1: Endorsing Environmental Protection (EEP)	($\alpha=0.609$)	
1. <i>Striving for environmental protection makes me feel worth while</i>		0.706
2. <i>Components of a green product are not harmful to animals and nature as compared to the other products</i>		0.635
3. <i>A green product generates the least amount of pollution in its usage</i>		0.434
4. <i>I feel environmental protection is not necessary</i>		-0.688
5. <i>Green products should be priced in line with value for money</i>		0.852
6. <i>For a green product, good value for money lies in its features</i>		0.612
7. <i>Components of eco-friendly products are recyclable</i>		0.602
8. <i>I find green products very relevant to my lifestyle</i>		0.511
9. <i>I prefer green products over non-green products when their product attributes are the same</i>		0.491
Factor 2: Perceived Environmental Responsibility (PER)	($\alpha=0.691$)	
10. <i>I should be responsible for protecting our environment and well being of the earth</i>		0.890
11. <i>Protecting the environment starts with me</i>		0.812
12. <i>Supporting environmental protection makes me feel like an environmentally responsible person</i>		0.677
13. <i>I am emotionally involved in environmental issues</i>		0.566
14. <i>Supporting environmental protection makes me feel sensible</i>		0.514
Factor 3: Consumers' Past Experience with Green Products (CEGP)	($\alpha=0.641$)	
15. <i>I share my experiences and knowledge about green products with my friend circle and somehow with unknown people</i>		0.856
16. <i>I buy green products, even if they are more expensive than non-green products</i>		0.702
17. <i>I make efforts to learn as much as I can about environmental issues</i>		0.564

18.	<i>I often take knowledge about green products from my friends or relatives</i>		0.445
Factor 4: Environmental Friendly Nature of Companies (EFNC)		($\alpha=0.850$)	
19.	<i>I like to buy brands that are less harmful to the environment</i>		0.878
20.	<i>I don't like to buy products from a company whose products harm the environment</i>		0.865
21.	<i>I often praise and promote eco-friendly brands</i>		0.807
Factor 5: Social Influence (SI)		($\alpha=0.624$)	
22.	<i>Others will perceive me "non-nature-oriented" and "out-dated" if I don't support environmental protection</i>		0.566
23.	<i>I maintain my pro-social reputation by supporting green products</i>		0.634
24.	<i>Supporting environmental issues makes me more socially appealing</i>		0.672
Green Product Purchase Decision (GPPD)		($\alpha=0.607$)	
25.	<i>I mostly buy products that use recycled or recyclable packaging</i>		0.612
26.	<i>I prefer to buy products that are environmentally friendly</i>		0.588
27.	<i>Even if I trust the performance of a green product, I will not pay more than a certain price level</i>		0.623

Table 5. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square
1	.764 ^a	.759

a. Predictors: (Constant), EEP, PER, CPEGP, EFNC, SI

Table 6. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	554.952	9	110.360	15.650	.000 ^b
	Residual	1547.732	186	7.140		
	Total	2102.684	195			

a. Dependent Variable: Var_GPPD
b. Predictors: (Constant), EEP, PER, CPEGP, EFNC, SI

Table 7. Coefficients^a

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	7.621	2.990		7.533	.000
	Endorsing Environmental Protection (EEP),	.363	.092	.168	2.464	.000
	Perceived Environmental Responsibility (PER),	.285	.072	.182	2.515	.000
	Consumers' Past Experience with Green Products (CPEGP),	.288	.065	.154	2.256	.000
	Environmental Friendly Nature of Companies (EFNC),	.385	.079	.214	2.960	.000
	Social Influence (SI)	.582	.095	.215	2.979	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Var_GPPD

Regression model was used to test the fitness of the model which was based on R value and R square. R value was 0.764 and R square was 0.759 which shows that the model is fit for our study. The model is significant as per the results of the given sample data which is shown in ANOVA with significance value being 0.000 where The F-test value of 15.650 is found significant which is much greater than 0.05 (See ANOVA Table 6). This also shows that the correlation between independent variables and the dependent variable is statistically significant and indicates the validity of the regression model. As we found 'R' = .764 as the Regression coefficient which indicates a positive correlation between independent variables and dependent variables. The coefficient of determination 'R²' = .759 indicate that 75.9% of the variation in the dependent variable is spelled out by independent variables (See ANOVA Table 6).

Standardized - coefficients in Table No.7 indicate the relative influence of GPPD on predictors. The highest number of Beta is 0.215 for "SI" which is significant at the 0.000 level. "EFNC" dimension also reflects a considerable amount of Beta which is 0.214 and is also significant at the 0.000 level and "PER" is also reflecting a considerable amount of Beta which is 0.182 and is too significant at the 0.000 level. This shows that there is a positive relationship

between psychological factors related to Green Product variables and Green Product Purchase Decision (GPPD). Although rest of the two factors having a considerable amount of Beta which is 0.168 and 0.154 at the significant level 0.000, for EEP and CPEGP respectively. This means that all variables significantly more or less impact the consumer's purchasing decision.

Hypotheses Testing

A regression table used to test the proposed hypotheses, the results are interpreted and discussed below in Table 8, and the relationship between green product purchase decision and Endorsing Environmental Protection (EEP), *Perceived* Environmental Responsibility (PER), Consumers' Past Experience with Green Products (CPEGP), Environmental Friendly Nature of Companies (EFNC) , and Social Influence (SI) were found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). And regression model clearly shows the impact of variables related to Endorsing Environmental Protection (EEP), *Perceived* Environmental Responsibility (PER), Consumers' Past Experience with Green Products (CPEGP), Environmental Friendly Nature of Companies (EFNC), and Social Influence (SI) has a great impact on green product purchase decision (GPPD).

Table 8. Result of Hypotheses Testing

S. No.	Hypotheses	P Value	Findings
H1	Endorsing Environmental Protection (EEP) significantly has an impact on consumers' green product purchase decisions (GPPD).	$p < 0.05$	Supported
H2	<i>Perceived</i> Environmental Responsibility (PER) significantly has an impact on consumers' green product purchase decisions (GPPD).	$p < 0.05$	Supported
H3	Consumers' Past Experience with Green Products (CPEGP) significantly has an impact on consumers' green product purchase decisions (GPPD).	$p < 0.05$	Supported
H4	Environmental Friendly Nature of Companies (EFNC) significantly has an impact on consumers' green product purchase decisions (GPPD).	$p < 0.05$	Supported
H5	Social Influence (SI) significantly has an impact on consumers' green product purchase decisions (GPPD).	$p < 0.05$	Supported

Discussion

Firstly, the study shows that most of the consumers are representatives of environmental protection and they prefer green products over non-green products as these are recyclable, produce the least pollution, and do not leave much waste to nature and these have now become a part of consumers' lifestyle. But they also want the price of green products to be as justified as the green features they offer, so more and more conscious people will continue to support environmental protection. Secondly, the study also shows that consumers understand the well-being of the planet, feel emotionally attached to environmental conservation, and believe that consumers should also be responsible for environmental threats and their conservation goals, which makes them sensible individuals.

Thirdly, the experience of green products is determined through physical actions, and perceptual and cognitive processes (perceiving, exploring, usage, recall, comparison, and understanding). The study found that this ranges from acquiring specific knowledge about the product, its features, and its characteristics to having memorable product-related experiences and product involvement. This exists in the forms of information search information sharing; and product use and/or ownership. Product experience related to information search and sharing explains the unique environmental features and characteristics of products. And, product experience related to use and/or ownership explains consumers' comprehensive understanding of the product and its features. Studies have found that this experience is facilitated either by consumers' own experience or by the experiences of others, which develops consumer perceptions about green products. The significant relationship between green product experience and green product purchase decisions reflects the role of functional, emotional, and experiential benefits of green products in the green product experience process in making green product purchase decisions. Therefore, marketing

professionals should promote green products in a way that provides opportunities to learn about green products and facilitates the sharing of information about green products.

Fourth, the study also found a significant relationship between companies' environmental friendliness and environmentally friendly consumer decisions. How companies' environmental friendliness affects consumers' green product purchasing behavior is revealed by the literature, which examines how information about companies' environmental behavior affects consumers' evaluations and perceptions of companies' environmental behavior and the environmental performance of their products. Therefore, the current study reveals that environmentally conscious consumers demand companies to behave in a responsible manner towards the environment. They prefer to buy products from companies that behave in a responsible manner towards the environment and vice versa, they refuse to buy products from companies that are found to be causing pollution. This will make marketers realize how important the environmental impact of their business activities is on the purchasing behavior of eco-friendly consumers.

Fifth and lastly, the study found a relationship between social influence and green product purchase decisions. This relationship suggests that others' perceptions of one's behavior significantly influence consumers' purchase behavior for green products. Consumers purchase green products if they are publicly recognized symbols of supporting environmental protection, express consumers' self-concept, and communicate desirable social meanings. People who want to achieve the social status of being ethical, ideologically motivated and environmentally responsible individuals adopt environmentally friendly lifestyles, purchase and consume green products. Therefore, when marketers launch green products in the Indian market, this finding can be useful for them for developing advertising campaigns and green products promotions.

The study demonstrates that it fully reflected the Protection Motivation Theory and Theory of Planned Behavior in green product purchase decisions by consumers. Rogers proposed the Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) in 1975 to demonstrate how fear factors affect health-related behaviors and attitudes. According to PMT, the cognitive resolution process is focused on the person's assessment of the threat when they are aware of it. According to Rogers, people will make an effort to avoid or flee a dangerous situation if they perceive it to be serious and threatening.

The theory of planned behavior (TPB) stands out as the most effective in forecasting human actions, and it can be managed in contrast to various psychological frameworks. The theory of reasoned action (TRA) was the foundation upon which the theory of planned behavior (TPB) was first developed. The TRA suggests that a customer's use of a product is influenced by their intention to use it, which is shaped by social norms (Ajzen, 2020). According to this theory, the risk of people undertaking a particular activity increases with a positive attitude towards the behavior, public acceptance of the behavior, and better control over the behavior. In recent times, lately, the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) has gained extensive application in research across various environmental issues, including water conservation and ecological attitudes (Zheng, et al., 2020). Our study seems to go towards both of these theories.

Implication of the Study

The prominence of awareness has motivated marketing managers of green products to seek information about environmentally friendly purchasing behavior. Therefore, with the gradual advancement in the green consumer research field, recent studies have focused on consumption-based studies to investigate the purchase behavior of green products. In this direction, current study has attempted to develop an understanding of consumers' perceptions about green products in reducing the impact of their consumption patterns on the environment. The findings of this study indicate

that Indian consumers have a level of environmental awareness that is reflected in their green product purchase decisions. They are concerned with environmental conservation issues, understand their responsibilities towards environmental conservation, believe in environmental problems and their solutions at the individual level, and search extensively for product-related ecological information and make environmentally friendly purchase decisions. They make their purchase decisions by examining and evaluating green products according to their expectations and past-self and peers experiences. Therefore, it can be inferred that the acceptance of green products depends on the environmental attributes of the products demanded by consumers.

The study investigated the relationships of several variables for their influence on green product purchase decisions, which have important theoretical contributions and managerial implications. First, the significant relationship between endorsing environmental protection and the perceiving environmental responsibility with green product purchase decisions confirms that the decision to purchase green products requires deliberate conscious evaluation of the environmental, personal, and social consequences associated with green products. This further indicates that consumers want to satisfy their functional, emotional and experiential needs which influence their purchase decisions. This reflects the relevance of eco-friendly lifestyle and green products to them in their consumption pattern. Therefore, marketing professionals of green products must explain how consumers' concerns about environmental protection and their responsibilities toward the environment are addressed through the purchase, use, and disposal of green products. Companies or marketers should analyze the environmental characteristics of green products and understand how they can be marketed so as to satisfy the specific desires of target segments. Such consumer-oriented approaches appear to be worthwhile for transforming consumers' support for environmental protection and

motivation for environmental responsibility into green product purchase decisions.

Conclusion

Thus, this study contributes scientifically to indicate the factors influencing green product purchase decisions in the Indian context. The study clearly demonstrates the importance of environmental sustainability and green product experience and eco-friendliness of companies in influencing Indian customers' decisions to purchase green items. In fact, the study shows that green product experience and environmental friendliness of companies are more important for Indian consumers in deciding to purchase green products than just the greenness of the product or their environmental consciousness. In addition, the study recognizes the role of supporting environmental protection and perceived environmental responsibility in making green product purchase decisions. This is consistent with findings from the literature that explain the roles of environmental concern, environmental activism, and perceived environmental responsibility in determining green consumer behavior. And, this study differs from earlier studies on green consumer behavior in explaining the relevance of social influence rather than social identity in making green product purchase decisions.

In other words, Indian consumers especially Delhites have environmental awareness and are concerned for environmental protection. Consumers actively endorse the environment by purchasing and consuming green products or eco-friendly products. Furthermore, they perceive personal and social meaning in their environmentally friendly activities and prefer to adopt environmentally friendly lifestyles. Not only this, Indian consumers try to know about green products, gain information about them and experience them. For this, they not only search for information about green products themselves but also take information from their friends and relatives. Consumers prefer to buy products from companies that behave in an environmentally responsible manner and,

conversely, they refuse to buy products from companies that are accused of causing pollution. They also share their experiences with green products and, thus, see social wisdom in endorsing environmental conservation issues. The findings of the study indicate that environmental awareness alone does not necessarily lead consumers to purchase green products. The study concludes that marketers should link green products to consumers' functional, emotional and experiential needs. Thus, this study enhances the understanding of green buyers in the Indian context and provides insights into understanding consumer demand for green products in the Indian market. But this study has some limitations, the sample data is collected from the metropolitan area of Delhi and it can represent the Indian population as it is considered as a mini India in terms of diversity. But still, given the constraints faced in collecting snowball sampling data, we can say that it does not reflect the overall consumers' expression across India.

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